

A STUDY ON JOB SATISFACTION OF NURSING STAFFS IN GOVERNMENT HOSPITAL AT MAYILADUTHURAI

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Abstract:

When persons are happy with their jobs, it improves their lives off the job. Some benefits of job satisfaction accrue to every citizen in society. Satisfied persons are more likely to be satisfied citizens. These people will hold a more positive attitude towards life in general treated as psychologically healthy people. So job satisfaction is very important. In contrast, the dissatisfied person carries that negative attitude at home. For management, a satisfied work force translates into higher productivity. Additionally, there are benefits for society in general due to job satisfaction. Satisfaction on the job carries over to the persons off the job hours. The goal of high job satisfaction for persons can be defended in terms of both money and social responsibility. The nursing staffs for both government and private hospital have lot of services rendering to the society. Their job satisfaction is in positive aspect to take more care for his patient. Therefore the present study is undertaken to find out the job satisfaction of nursing staffs in government hospital at mayiladuthurai town.

Key Words: Job Satisfaction, Environment, Factor Analysis, Communication & Organization

Introduction:

Job satisfaction is a combination of psychological, physiological & environment circumstances that cause a person to say. One way to define job satisfaction may be to say that it is experienced after a task is accomplished or an activity has taken place whether it is highly individualistic effort of writing a book or a collective Endeavour of constructing a building. These activities may be minute or large. But in all cases, they satisfy a certain need. The feeling could be positive or negative depending upon whether need is satisfied or not situational opportunities available to him. Person may experience positive job satisfaction because he has been chosen to complete the task. It gives him a special status & feeling that he has been trusted and give a special task, he likes such kind of rush job and it may get him extra wages. The same could be the sources of his dissatisfaction if he does not like rush work, has no need for extra wages. Each of these variables led to an end state of feeling, called satisfaction.

Determination of job satisfaction there are organizational variables and personal variables. Organizational variables such as occupational level, job content, considerate leadership, pay and promotional opportunities, interaction in the work group etc., personal variable like that age, educational level role perception and sex. Some other determinate of job satisfaction are general working conditions, grievance handling procedure, fair evaluation of work done, job security.

Statement of the Problem:

It is the motto of the state to provide cheap and best medical facility to the down trodden and the common folk. In order to achieve thus motto the government is maintaining a lot of hospitals in the taluk and districts head quarters throughout the state. On the other hand the villagers are deprived of the medical facilities in their native villages. They are not affordable to get better treatment for their ills in private clinics. In order to fulfill this, the government is running primary health centers in a

cluster of five six villages besides there are a lot of well trained nursing staff to look after the health needs of the villagers and to save them from the quacks. In the job the government nursing fraternity faces a lot of problems in their day to day official work. The researcher with an enthusiasm, wanted to study their mental and physical satisfaction over their job.

Scope of the Study:

This study would help to all job satisfaction facility to the primary health centre’s and government nursing staff. Thus finding of the present study would therefore enable the researcher to suggest suitable preventive, measures that would make awareness about the nursing staff’s basic demands and needs problems etc.

Objectives:

- ✓ To identify the job satisfaction among the employees of nursing staff member in government hospitals.
- ✓ To analyse the factors that influence the job satisfaction.
- ✓ To know whether the employees are satisfied with the facilities provided by the organization.

Research Methodology:

Data collection is the most important task for any type of research. The study is based on both primary and secondary data. Primary data were collected from the employees of the sample unit with help of well structured questionnaires. The secondary data were collected from journals, magazines, Books and internet, which are more relevant to the study.

Sampling:

The size of the total sample for the present study is 50 in a Mayiladuthurai town. The sample units are selected according to the convenience of the researcher. Here, the researcher used convenience sample design for collection of primary data through structured questionnaires.

Data Analysis:

Data were collected through primary sources, from the government hospital nursing staffs at Mayiladuthurai. The study has been made 50 respondents available in study area. The researcher have framed questionnaire in various level of job satisfaction in working place were as follow;

Table 1: Job satisfaction of the nursing staff members

Measured Variable	Level of Job satisfaction					No. of Respondents	%
	Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Average	Dissatisfied	Highly Dissatisfied		
Working Environment	21 (42%)	24 (48%)	5 (10%)	-	-	50	100
Welfare Measures	20 (40%)	20 (40%)	10 (20%)	-	-	50	100
Safety Measures	19 (38%)	25 (50%)	16 (12%)	-	-	50	100
Relationship	28 (56%)	10 (20%)	7 (14%)	1 (2%)	-	50	100
Monitory Policy	12 (24%)	17(34%)	16 (32%)	5 (10%)	-	50	100
Promotion Policy	35(70%)	10 (20%)	5 (10%)	-	-	50	100

Source: primary Data

Findings:

- ✓ The following are the major findings of the study:

Personal Data:

- ✓ The majority of the respondents i.e., 70 had married and 30 of them had unmarried.
- ✓ 62% of the respondents had completed B.Sc., in nursing and 38% of them had completed diploma in nursing.
- ✓ It is clear that 84% of the nursing staff members are belongs to below 10 years and 12% of the respondents experience between 10 to 20 years and 2% of the respondents from 20 to 30 years of working experience.

Working Environment:

- ✓ From the above analysis, 48% of respondents are satisfied and 42% of respondents are highly satisfied and 10% of them were average with their working environment.
- ✓ It is clear that 36% of respondents are satisfied and 34% of respondents are highly satisfied with their maintenance of equipments.

Welfare Measures:

- ✓ It is noted that 40% of respondents satisfied and another 40% of them highly satisfied and remaining 20% of the employees felt average.
- ✓ From the study, 36% of respondents are average with their canteen facilities provided by the hospital, 30% are highly satisfied, 20% of the respondents are satisfied and remaining is dissatisfied.

Safety Measures:

- ✓ Half of the nursing staff members i.e., 50% felt satisfied about their first aid kit and 12% felt average and 38% felt highly satisfied.
- ✓ The training for fire extinguisher of the nursing staff members in government hospital, 36% of the respondents felt average, 34% felt highly satisfied, 28% of the staff members are satisfied and remaining 2% of them dissatisfied.

Relationship:

- ✓ It is noted that half of the respondents 56% of them highly satisfied about their relation in between management and employee, 20% of the respondents are satisfied, 14% felt average and 2% were dissatisfied.
- ✓ It is clear that half of the nursing staffs i.e., 44% felt satisfied about their training social interaction among co-workers and 36% of the respondents are felt highly satisfied and 16% were average and 4% of them dissatisfied.

Monitory Policy:

- ✓ From the study, 34% were satisfied about their salary and 32% of them average, 24% were highly satisfied, remaining 10% of the nursing staffs are dissatisfied.

Personal Policy:

- ✓ Promotion policy of nursing staff members in government hospital as per norms of government rules and regulation policy is applicable for permanent employee. From the above analysis 70% of the respondents were represented highly satisfied about their promotion policy.
- ✓ It is noted that, 52% of respondents were represented satisfied about their job rotation.

Suggestions:

- ✓ The nursing staffs are to be strictly ordered to live in their head quarters.
- ✓ The staffs are to be advised that they should not wait for the arrival of the sick people to the health center but to go to door steps.
- ✓ The government may follow the transfer policy of at least the nursing staff are not transferred from one place to another within three years.

- ✓ The salary bills, travelling allowances and conveyance are to be given to the staff without hindrance and then only the morale of the nursing staff will stand good.

Conclusion:

The study examined the job satisfaction of nursing staff at government hospital. Just more than half of the respondents satisfied and highly satisfied. Feeling that nursing is worthwhile and satisfying and financial stability at the hospital could promote staff retention. Specific intrinsic – welfare measure, safety measure, monetary policy with supervisors and organizational support of the few respondents are feeling average. The nursing administrator must implement the commitment, so that the ideals of the organization and needs of nurses can be congruent to ensure a consistent flow of trained and satisfied manpower in the future.

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